

Acknowledgements

We extend our thanks to Sarah Challenger and Lucy Thomson at the Cawthron Institute for assistance with lab work and microalgal culture. We also thank the Scott Base staff and all members of the K892 and K043 field teams for logistics support and assistance in sampling. We thank Svenja Halfter, Ollie Twigge and Stacy Deppler (NIWA) for sample collection and logistics as part of the 2023 NIWA RV Tangaroa voyage. We thank Antarctica New Zealand for their financial and logistic support via the Sir Robert Irvine Doctoral Scholarship (J.S.). New Zealand's National Institute for Water and Atmospheric Research [NIWA; Contract COAO404] and Antarctic Science Platform [Contract ANTA1801] supported multiple field sampling seasons, as well as time for NR, KR. The FORST Foundation of Research Science and technology also supported earlier field seasons and time for KR. This work was funded by the Ministry of Business, Innovation and Employment Strategic Science Investment Fund (SSIF) Seafood Safety research,

contract number CAWX1801. Additionally, we extend our gratitude to Victoria University of Wellington for their financial support via a Doctoral Scholarship and Faculty of Science Grant 400086 (J.S.).

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14364072>

First report of *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* exceeding alert thresholds in Bay of Plentzia (South-East Bay of Biscay)

Fig. 1. Location of the sampling site.

Several species of benthic dinoflagellates belonging to the genus *Ostreopsis* are potentially toxic and were originally distributed mostly in warm and tropical

waters. Their presence has been associated with several toxic episodes affecting humans, with symptoms including dermatological and respiratory issues

[1]. Palytoxin analogues, including ova-toxins, ostreocins and liguriatoxins, have been proposed as the toxins responsible for these health issues, although no direct evidence has yet been established [2, 3].

Since *Ostreopsis* was first reported in the Basque Country in 2007 [4], there has been a notable increase in its abundance and distribution along the Basque coast, and it is now common during the summer months [5, 6]. Notably, during summer 2021, *Ostreopsis* cell densities exceeded the alert threshold for the first time in the Bay of Biscay, resulting in the closure of several beaches. Chomérat *et al.* [7] determined that the blooms observed in the French Basque coast during summer 2021 were not monospecific, containing both *Ostreopsis cf. siamensis* and *Ostreopsis cf. ovata*, with the latter confirmed as the toxin producer. Concurrently, high densities of *Ostreopsis* spp. were also observed in San Sebastián on the Spanish Basque coast, where respiratory problems were reported among sunbathers. This

prompted the development of a monitoring programme to gain insight into the seasonal dynamics of this genus in coastal waters of the Basque Country.

One of the selected areas for intensified summer sampling was the sheltered Bay of Plentzia (Fig. 1), a popular summer destination in Biscay. The sampling site, located in the northernmost part of the bay in a rocky intertidal area beyond the breakwater protecting Astondo beach, is semi-exposed to the open sea. The rocky seabed is rich in macroalgae growing in intertidal pools. Between June and early September, six samplings were conducted in both summer 2023 (20 June–1 August) and summer 2024 (26 June–4 September). *Ostreopsis* spp. cells were quantified through light microscope counts of water column samples (cells·L⁻¹) and epiphytic samples (cells·g⁻¹). For the latter samples, five macroalgal species were sampled due to changes in macroalgal community dominance: *Centroceras clavulatum*, *Cladostephus spongiosus*, *Dictyota* sp., *Ellisolandia elongata*, and *Halopteris scoparia*. Alert thresholds that have

been established for the north-western Mediterranean were taken into consideration [2]. Environmental variables were also characterised and molecular analyses were conducted to identify the different *Ostreopsis* species.

Blooms of *Ostreopsis* spp. occurred during the summer months of both 2023 and 2024 in the Bay of Plentzia. Abundances (Fig. 2) remained below 250 cells·L⁻¹ and 1600 cells·g⁻¹ in June and July of both years. However, from August towards the end of the summer period there was a marked increase in both the planktonic and the epiphytic abundances of *Ostreopsis* spp., with 1.59 × 10⁴ cells·L⁻¹ and 3.07 × 10⁴ cells·g⁻¹ on 18 August 2023, or 1.05 × 10⁴ cells·L⁻¹ and 5.45 × 10⁴ cells·g⁻¹ on August 20 2024. On 4 September 2024, the maximum *Ostreopsis* spp. abundances of the study were recorded in both the planktonic and the epiphytic samples (3.55 × 10⁴ cells·L⁻¹ and 9.54 × 10⁴ cells·g⁻¹), even exceeding the alert threshold established for the water column in the Mediterranean region [2]. These blooms coincided with consist-

ently warm waters exceeding 20.5 °C, peaking at 23.6 °C on 18 August 2023. This is consistent with findings of other studies [1], which associate *Ostreopsis* spp. blooms in temperate areas with water temperatures between 20°C and 29 °C. Elevated oxygen saturation levels (>109%) accompanied the highest abundances of *Ostreopsis*, reflecting the extensive macroalgal coverage of the site's rocky sea floor. Salinity and pH showed minimal variation, with ranges of 32.9–34.4 and 8.13–8.39, respectively, making their impact on blooms unclear.

Eight *Ostreopsis* strains isolated from the water column are now deposited at the Basque Microalgae Culture Collection (BMCC) at the University of the Basque Country. The amplification of the ITSA and ITSB rDNA regions confirmed that the eight strains belonged to *O. cf. siamensis*. Further studies, including qPCR and metabarcoding, will enable the detection of other potentially present *Ostreopsis* species, such as *O. cf. ovata*.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by the 'One Health Observatory Lighthouse (HOBE)' research project. We thank the BMCC team for their help during the samplings.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14364118>

Fig. 2. Planktonic (top) and epiphytic (down) abundances of *Ostreopsis* spp. (bars) and water temperature (line) in summer 2023 and summer 2024. The distinctive bar pattern indicates that the alert threshold established by [2] for planktonic samples, 3 × 10⁴ cells·L⁻¹, was exceeded. The alert threshold established for epiphytic samples, 2 × 10⁵ cells·g⁻¹ was not exceeded.